

Forest Soil indicators: The Role of Pasture Management

www.af4eu.eu

Both forests and grasslands provide the necessary pasture, supporting biodiversity and wildlife. The sustainable management of these ecosystems, as well as pastures, offers numerous benefits, enhancing the livestock productivity of livestock, while contributing to biodiversity and soil protection. Soil quality indicators, such as soil organic matter, pH, texture, moisture, biodiversity, etc., provide useful information on the condition of forest soils and the effectiveness of management practices in pastures. Pasture management aims to maintain and improve soil quality, especially at a time when factors such as climate change, desertification and other pressures may accelerate the process of soil degradation.

For example, an innovative grazing practice applied in the mountainous areas of *Evrytania* in Greece is the combined grazing and coexistence of different livestock species, such as sheep, goats, cattle, horses in the same pastures (by rotation).

This practice enhances the more efficient use of vegetation, since each species has different dietary preferences, ensuring the most efficient use of biomass. At the same time, the dispersion of organic matter over the whole surface of the pasture, through the faeces, helps to improve soil fertility. Furthermore, it reduces the presence of weeds, balances the pressure on the pasture, reduces soil compaction at specific points and minimises the risk of soil erosion and degradation. Simultaneously, the economic benefits are multiple, enabling farmers to use products from different types of livestock, such as meat, milk, wool and hides, while reducing the cost of soil restoration.

In conclusion, key indicators of soil health can contribute to the formulation of sustainable grazing plans. Pasture management can contribute to the long-term health of both pastures and forest ecosystems by promoting a balance between productive agricultural use and environmental conservation.

Grazing and forest soils. Silvopastorals in Evrytania (photo by Vappa)

**Stavroula Galanopoulou,
Anastasia Pantera, Vassiliki
Lappa, Andreas
Papadopoulos**

Department of forestry &
Natural Environment Management,
Karpenissi, Greece

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.